

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEPRESSIVE PATHOLOGY AND THE PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENTS**Sattarov T.**

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Abstract

Objective Purpose: to study the features of depressive symptoms in adolescents to optimize therapeutic and preventive measures. **Material and methods:** 111 adolescents aged 15 to 17 years, with the presence of depressive symptoms, were examined in the departments of the Clinical Hospital of the city of Tashkent. The Zung scale was used to determine the severity of depression and the Lichko questionnaire to establish character accentuation. **Results:** an analysis of the features of depressive symptoms in adolescents established the presence of a predominance of behavioral disorders in the clinical picture of the disease with a tendency to use psychoactive substances, disorders of intra-family relationships, and dysphoric reactions. **Conclusion:** Thus, the study of the features of depressive symptoms in adolescents found that dysphoric depression with significant behavioral disorders in persons with epileptoid character accentuation and anxiety depression in persons with psychasthenic character traits are most often formed during puberty. The results obtained will make it possible to identify important personal targets of psychotherapeutic work with patients prone to the development of depressive symptoms.

Keywords: adolescents; personal characteristics; emotional disorders; depression.

Introduction: Over the past decades, there has been a rapid increase in suicidal tendencies of depressive genesis among children and adolescents. The relevance of the problem of depressive behavioral disorders in children and adolescents is caused by the difficulties of timely verification of affective pathology, the expediency of correctly chosen pharmacotherapy and the difficulties in predicting these mental disorders [1]. In children and adolescents, depressive pathology, in contrast to the adult population, in rare cases, clinically occurs with the classic symptoms of the depressive triad - lowering mood, slowing down thinking and motor activity [3]. Most often, the clinical picture of depression is atypical, characterized by the obliteration of the main symptoms, disguise as other diseases, and the predominance of somatovegetative disorders [2,4]. According to a number of authors, a psychiatrist consulted only 27% of children with a depressive onset of the disease during their first depression; general somatic specialists observed the rest for a long time [9]. At the initial visit to a psychiatrist, a depressive state was found only in 23.6% of cases due to the lack of expression of affective disorders proper, the prevalence of complaints of behavioral disorders, including aggressiveness, school maladaptation, and computer addiction [8]. In the puberty period, there is an increase in depressive symptoms against the background of ideas of one's own inferiority and dysmorphophobic inclinations with a tendency to antisocial behavior, which were not diagnosed in a timely manner due to the presence of an unhealthy microclimate in the family and the lack of mutual understanding between children and parents [5, 7, 10]. First, depressive states in adolescence and adolescence are associated with destructive forms of behavior, the extreme variant of which is suicidal behavior. Behavioral disorders and patho-characterological reactions of protest and opposition, interpersonal conflicts with peers and teachers are specific features of pubertal depression [6, 11].

The purpose of the study: study the features of depressive symptoms in adolescents, taking into account characterological personality traits and a tendency to suicidal tendencies.

Material and methods of the study: 111 adolescents aged up to 19 years inclusive, 78 boys and 33 girls (average age 16.96 ± 1.98 years) who were admitted for inpatient treatment in the adolescent departments of the City Clinical Psychiatric Hospital were chosen as the object for the study the Tashkent city with the presence of depressive disorders. The clinical and psychopathological method was used to identify the leading psychopathological syndrome at the time of examination. All established diagnoses were based on the tenth revision criteria of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). We determined the personality traits of adolescents (PAD) using the Modified Patho-characterological Diagnostic Questionnaire (MDPO Lichko A.E., Ivanov N.Ya. 2001). We identified depressive disorders using the Zung Depression Self-Assessment Scale (ZDRS) (L.I. Wasserman, O.Yu. Shchelkova, 1995).

Results and their discussion: at the initial stage of our study, we studied the features of clinical manifestations of depressive pathology in adolescents. According to the classification of child psychiatrist E.G. Eidemiller (2005), in adolescence, depressive symptoms are divided into adolescent depressive equivalents - delinquent, asthenopathic, anxious, hypochondriacal, which mask the typical classic triad of depression, are perceived as features of the puberty period and make diagnosis and treatment very difficult. In our study, all adolescents were divided into five groups depending on the prevalence of the leading symptom of depression - dysphoric, anxious, dysmorphophobic, asthenopathic and masked. Dysphoric depression was clinically manifested by outbreaks of a melancholy-angry mood, conflict, aggression, rudeness towards adults, especially towards parents and close relatives against the background of a low psycho-emotional

state. Such behavior provokes the formation of intra-family conflicts, deterioration of the microclimate in the family, punishment and beatings of the child for bad behavior, which ultimately contributes to running away from home and vagrancy, and leads the teenager to asocial companies. In the clinical manifestations of dysphoric depression, we have identified addictive forms of behavioral disorders: a tendency to aggression and physical violence, petty offenses, theft, running away from home and vagrancy, smoking, early alcoholization and episodic use of psychoactive substances.

In our study, dysphoric depression was verified more often (in 33 adolescents) than other types, and was mainly observed in boys with socialized conduct disorder. Adolescents with anxious depression against the background of low mood had a feeling of expectation of a danger of an uncertain nature, which formed an idea of an unfavorable development of events, adolescents were in a state of constant tension, in the grip of bad forebodings, they observed somatovegetative reactions, restlessness and restlessness, behavior that was inadequate to the real situation. Anxious depression was found in 30 teenagers of the surveyed group. Dymorphophobic depression was observed only in 14 (12.61%) adolescent girls. The clinical picture of dymorphophobic depression was dominated by complaints of a sense of inferiority, the presence of physical disabilities, inconsistency with the standards and standards of beauty, unlike anorexia nervosa, girls with dymorphophobic depression did not seek to change themselves by following diets and restrictive eating behavior, but, on the contrary, were passive and dejected, they noted a feeling of low value, worthlessness, uselessness due to the presence of excess weight and flaws in appearance. Such states were accompanied by a de-

crease in appetite against the background of hypothy-mia and the appearance of rudimentary ideas of self-abasement. In the clinical picture of asthenoapathic depression, the leading complaints were fatigue and weakness, loss of strength, decreased motor activity, poor tolerance for large crowds of people, inability to be in the company of peers and classmates, communication difficulties, inactivity, feelings of boredom and despondency. The presence of this symptomatology caused in a teenager a desire for loneliness, a feeling of inferiority, worthlessness, a violation of relationships with parents and relatives, a disorder in school adaptation and the formation of suicidal thoughts and intentions. The lowered background of mood in asthenoapathic depression is incorrectly interpreted as apathy, most likely it is the paucity of manifestations of a decrease in mood. A variant of asthenoapathic depression occurred in 14 adolescents who complained to a greater extent of weakness, tearfulness, rapid exhaustion and fatigue. In patients with masked depression, in the foreground there were complaints of a hypochondriacal nature of somatic symptoms, such adolescents aggravated with existing somatic diseases, against the background of low mood, lack of appetite, increased fatigue, refused to attend school classes and lessons, prepare homework, help around the house. The clinical picture of masked depression was also dominated by behavioral disorders in the form of refusing to eat, do household chores, lack of motivation for vigorous activity, playing sports or attending circles and various events, there was a violation of the adaptive abilities of adolescents in communication with peers and schoolteachers. Interpersonal relationships were limited to the circle of relatives and friends. Masked depression occurred in 20 patients of the study sample (Fig. 1.).

Fig. 1. Clinical forms of depressive symptoms in adolescents.

For a detailed study of the personality traits of adolescents, we used the Modified Pathocharacterological Diagnostic Questionnaire (MPDO) by A.E. Lichko and N.Y. Ivanov with an improved procedure for processing the results. According to the survey data, adolescents were divided according to character accentuations. Adolescents with a hysterical personality were statistically significantly prevalent in the main group of the study (41.1%), in contrast to adolescents in the comparison group (20.0%, $p < 0.045$). Similar results were obtained in adolescents with affective (24.6% of patients in the main and 4.0% of patients in the comparison group; $p < 0.003$) and epileptoid (26.2% of patients in the main and 8.0% of patients in the comparison group; $p < 0.01$) personality warehouse. In the comparison group, there was a statistically significant predominance of adolescents with unstable (1.6% of patients in the main and 14.0% of patients in the comparison group; $p < 0.045$). Psychasthenic (4.9% of patients in the main and 42.0% of patients in the comparison group; $p < 0.001$) and hyperthymic (1.6% of patients in the main and 12.0% of patients in the comparison group; $p < 0.045$) character accentuation. The correlation between the presence or absence of suicidal tendencies and the personality traits of adolescents was average in strength ($C = 0.51$, $p < 0.001$). Thus, the intergroup analysis of the results of the study determined that adolescents with epileptoid, affective and hysteroid

type of character accentuation can be included in the risk group for the development of suicidal tendencies. Adolescents with epileptoid character traits were prone to the formation of potentially dangerous suicidal tendencies against the background of sudden strong affect. Suicidal tendencies in adolescents with hysteroid accentuation of character were marked by demonstrative-blackmail and manipulative nature, but under the confluence of adverse circumstances they posed a threat to life. In adolescents with an affective type of character, the intensity of suicidal tendencies increased in the subdepressive phase, in being alone against the background of a reduced psycho-emotional state as a result of conflicts with parents and peers.

At the next stage of the study, with the help of MPDO, A.E. Lichko, we have identified the personality characteristics of adolescents in the form of character accentuations. Among them, 35 (31.5%) adolescents have a hysterical temperament, 17 (15.3%) have an affective temperament, 20 (18.1%) have an epileptoid type, 8 (7.2%) have an unstable personality type, psychasthenic - 24 (21.6%) and hyperthymic - 7 (6.3%) adolescents. No less interesting for the study was the study of the correlation between the clinical form of depression and the type of accentuation of the teenager's character. The distribution of adolescents with different types of character accentuation depending on the clinical form of depression is shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Types of character accentuation and clinical form of depression

Types of depression	Type of character accentuation						
	hysterical	affective	epileptoid	Psychasthenic	Hyperthymic	Unstable	Total
	abs. %	abs. %	abs. %	abs. %	abs. %	abs. %	abs. %
Dysphoric	10/9.0	2/1.8	20/18.0*	—	1/0.9	2/1.8	35/31.5
Anxious	3/2.7	13/11.7	—	14/12.6*	—	—	30/27.0
Asthenoapatic	6/5.4	1/0.9	—	4/3.6	—	3/2.7	14/12.6
Dysmorphic-phobic	13/11.7*	—	—	1/0.9	—	—	14/12.6
Masked	3/2.7	1/0.9	—	5/4.5	6/5.4	3/2.7	18/16.2
Total	35/31.5	17/15.4	20/18.0	24/21.6	7/6.3	8/7.2	111/100

Note: *significance of differences $p < 0.045$

A comparative analysis of the distribution of adolescents with different types of character accentuation, depending on the clinical form of depression, revealed a relative predominance of dysphoric depression in adolescents with epileptoid character accentuation (18.0%), however, statistically significant differences with adolescents with hysteroid accentuation (9.0%, $p > 0.05$). Affective (1.8%, $p > 0.05$), hyperthymic (0.9%, $p > 0.05$) and unstable (1.8%, $p > 0.05$) type of character accentuation according to this indicator was not found. Anxious depression was more often observed in adolescents with a psychasthenic personality

(12.6%), although there were statistically significant differences with hysterical (2.7%; $p > 0.05$) and affective (11.7%, $p > 0.05$) warehouse identity was not found. Asthenoapathic depression was more often observed in hysterical personalities (5.4%), however, significant differences with affective (0.9%; $p > 0.05$), psychasthenic (3.6%; $p > 0.05$) and unstable (2.7%; $p > 0.05$) no warehouse has been established. Dysmorphic-phobic depression occurred in 11.7% of adolescents with hysteroid accentuation of character; however, differences with psychasthenic personalities (0.9%; $p > 0.05$) on this basis did not have statistical significance.

Hyperthymic (5.4%) individuals were relatively more likely to be diagnosed with hypochondriacal depression, but there were statistically significant differences with adolescents with hysteroid (2.7%, $p>0.05$), affective (0.9%, $p>0.05$), psychasthenic (4.5%, $p>0.05$) and unstable (2.7%, $p>0.05$) types of character accentuation was not revealed by this indicator. The correlation of the clinical form of depression with premorbid typological personality traits was quite strong ($C=0.71$, $p<0.001$) and exceeded the correlation with the nosological affiliation of the depressive disorder.

Conclusions: research of the relationship between depressive pathology and the personal characteristics of adolescents reveals some phenomena - thus, the study of the features of depressive symptoms in adolescents found that dysphoric depressions with significant behavioral disorders in persons with epileptoid accentuation of character and anxious depressions in persons with psychasthenic character traits are most often formed in the puberty period. The results obtained will allow us to identify important personal targets of psychotherapeutic work with patients prone to the development of depressive symptoms.

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